

A Client-Weighted Medium-Transparent MAC protocol for User-Centric Fairness in 60 GHz Radio-over-Fiber WLANs

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Abstract— We present a novel Client-Weighted Medium-Transparent MAC (CW-MT-MAC) protocol with enhanced fairness service delivery properties accompanied by a low-loss Remote Access Unit (RAU) architecture for use in indoor, Gbps capable, 60 GHz Radio-over-Fiber (RoF) Wireless Local Access Networks (WLANs). Our approach relies on incorporating a Client Weighted Algorithm (CWA) in the optical capacity allocation mechanism employed in the MT-MAC scheme, so as to distribute the available wavelengths to the different antenna units according to the total number of active users served by each individual antenna. The protocol's throughput and delay fairness characteristics are evaluated and validated through both simulations and analytic modeling for saturated network traffic operational conditions. In addition, extended simulation-based performance analysis for non-saturated network conditions and for different end-user distributions, traffic loads and available optical wavelengths at 1 Gbps data rates are presented. Our results confirm that complete throughput equalization can be achieved even for highly varying user population patterns when certain wavelength availability conditions are satisfied. At the same time, the presented scheme manages to equalize the average packet delays amongst packets generated by all RAUs while concurrently dropping the Packet Delay Variation (PDV) metric that is essential for Quality of Service (QoS) delivery. Finally the

proposed RAU design reduces insertion losses by almost 14dB compared to RAU elements used in MT-MAC-compatible bus networks, extending in this way the number of supported RAUs by an order of magnitude and enabling the formation of extended reach, high-speed RoF WLANs.

Index Terms— Fiber/Wireless; Radio-over-Fiber; Medium-Transparent MAC; 60GHz WLANs. Remote Access Unit

I. INTRODUCTION

Nowadays we bear witness to the strong commercial interest in utilizing the 60 GHz band towards providing ultra-fast Gbps-capable access network environments as can be attested by the significant number of recently issued 60 GHz standards such as the 802.11ad[1], the 802.15.3c[2], the WirelessHD[3] and the ECMA 387[4]. However, the unprecedented 60 GHz capacity comes at the cost of picocellular coverage due to the inherent ultra-high propagation losses. This inevitably limits mm-wave connectivity to Personal Area Networking (PAN) applications [1]-[5], offering Gbps wireless links only to end users residing in the same physical area and at a radius no greater than a few meters from the access point.

As such, the effort towards extending 60GHz communication to Wireless Local Area Network (WLAN) applications cannot proceed along the paradigm of overlapping cells that cover a greater area, as the dense deployment of fully functional access points would render the cost prohibitive. To this end, hybrid Fiber/Wireless (FiWi) technologies have been proposed as a candidate technology that can facilitate the cost-effective realization of 60GHz WLANs, effectively combining the high-capacity of optical fiber backhauling infrastructure with the ubiquity and flexibility of wireless connections[6]-[7]. Among the FiWi schemes, Radio-over-Fiber (RoF) solutions seem to be a good fit for 60GHz WLANs since they transfer all necessary intelligent functionalities to a centralized location and substitute the fully functional Access Points (APs) with Remote Access Units (RAUs) that act solely as RF/optical signal converters, thus cutting costs and making dense RAU deployment feasible[8],[9].

However, the majority of research revolving around RoF

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has focused mainly on the physical layer enabling technologies[10]-[13] and only a limited number of attempts for functional architectures including Medium Access Control Mechanisms over RoF infrastructures has been reported so far [14]-[19]. The latter have either focused on exploiting the underlying fiber infrastructure strictly as a passive distribution network used for the purpose of long-distance data delivery [14]-[17] or have exclusively relied on methods for the direct adaptation of already existing wireless MAC protocols onto the RoF-backhauled environment [8],[18]-[19], treating actually the optical network part as a passive point-to-point link. Such an approach does certainly not favor the seamless interplay of currently distinct optical/wireless functional portfolios. In addition, it can hardly cope with the large number of RAUs foreseen in a mm-wave WLAN scenario, since it assumes a static resource allocation scheme and/or 1-to-1 relationship between wavelengths and RAUs.

The first available 60GHz RoF WLAN network architecture that employs dynamically reconfigurable bandwidth mechanisms both in the optical and the 60GHz wireless network parts has been demonstrated by the authors in [20],[21] through the introduction of a Medium-Transparent MAC (MT-MAC) protocol. The MT-MAC protocol concept demonstrated the successful connectivity between wireless end-users who are served even by different 60GHz RAUs, effectively expanding Gbps-scale mm-wave communication into an extended WLAN area when exploiting the seamless interplay between optical and wireless capacity arbitration processes. More recently, a multi-channel resource allocation scheme relying on the MT-MAC mechanism has been presented towards enriching the mm-wave WLAN environment with handover capability [22]. However, both the MT-MAC protocol mechanism as well as its associated network architecture presented in [20]-[22] yield certainly a sub-optimal performance when it comes to more practical network scenarios: (a) its physical layer optical bus architecture scales only up to a few RAUs as it relies on a high-loss configuration, which is the result of its non-optimized design and of a high insertion loss RAU layout, and (b) it employs a simple Round-Robin algorithm for distributing the optical capacity among the different RAU elements, negating in this way user fairness in the case of uneven user population distributions per RAU. Towards coping with user fairness in 60GHz RoF-based WLANs, we have recently introduced a Client-Weighted MT-MAC (CW-MT-MAC) protocol mechanism [23] that has been demonstrated solely through simulation results to provide enhanced user fairness conditions under various network loads.

In this paper, we extend our previous work on CW-MT-MAC and present a novel low-loss RAU architecture for increasing the bus network dimensions, demonstrating at the same time an extensive simulation-based performance analysis and a complete mathematical model for the CW-MT-MAC protocol in saturation conditions. The new RAU design exhibits significantly lower insertion losses when compared to equivalent MT-MAC-compatible RAU designs reported in [20]-[23], allowing for an increase of the bus network-supported RAUs by an order of magnitude .

Moreover, we provide an analytical model followed by a detailed saturation throughput performance analysis for the CW-MT-MAC protocol, assuming ideal channel conditions. The introduced model relies on a 2-D Markov chain approach for calculating the end-user transmission probabilities, taking into account variable user distribution standard deviation values. An analytic formula for throughput computation is derived and the respective results for different optical resource availability factors and for data rates up to 1 Gbps are found to be in close agreement with simulation-based findings. Finally, we present an extensive performance evaluation of our protocol for 1 Gbps data rates, showing that the CW-MT-MAC can balance out end-user throughput and delay inequalities, while significantly decreasing and equating the user-perceived PDV even in highly deviating population distributions amongst the network's RAUs, significantly outperforming the MT-MAC protocol with respect to end user fairness.

The paper is outlined as follows: Section II presents the state of the art regarding 60GHz schemes and hybrid Fiber/Wireless networks. Section III presents the architectural overview of the proposed RAU module. Section IV describes the MT-MAC protocol characteristics with the emphasis set on the Client Weighted optical capacity allocation scheme and provides its mathematical performance analysis. Section V presents the performance evaluation through an extensive series of analytical and simulation tests. Section VI concludes the paper.

II. 60 GHz OVER HYBRID OPTICAL/WIRELESS NETWORKS

The worldwide harmonization and the license exempt property of the 60GHz band have fueled the industry's efforts towards the development of standards capable of harnessing the immense 7GHz bandwidth capacity available in the millimeter-wave band. However, due to the very high frequency and inherent oxygen absorption, the propagation of millimeter radio wave is strongly hindered by attenuation, exhibiting up to 30dB higher propagation losses than that of 2,4-5GHz bands under the same antenna gains[24]. Therefore the vast majority of the released standards target short-range wireless personal area networking (WPAN) applications [2]-[4] such as fast file syncing, wireless docking, cable replacement and high-speed kiosk data transfers. The first presented 60GHz WPAN standard is the IEEE 802.15.3c [2]. 802.15.3c supports 1 Gbps data rates for applications such as real-time HD video streaming as well as very high data rates in excess of 2 Gbps for point-to-point wireless data bus cable replacement. ECMA 387 [4] is another 60GHz WPAN standard finalized in 2008 that supports multiple device types and various data speeds of up to 6Gbps when employing a channel aggregation method referred as channel bonding. WirelessHD [3] is an industrial consortium standard specifically developed to function as a multimedia point-to-point transmission protocol for consumer devices and is able to achieve theoretical data rates of 25 Gbps when exploiting the whole 7GHz bandwidth available. All the above standards provide

Fig. 1 Network configuration over bus topology.

device-to-device multi-Gbps connectivity over short ranges (<10 meters), and as such, apply only to cases where the wireless users reside within the same confined physical space and require one-to-one device connectivity services.

A. 60 GHz in WLANs

Regarding Wireless Local Area Networks (WLANs) we witness that far less produced work exists in the mm-wave domain, with the only available standard today being the IEEE 802.11ad[1]. 802.11ad has been very recently released and is the product of joint collaboration between IEEE's 802.11 task group and the WiGig [25] industrial consortium. 802.11ad is a tri-band operating protocol that maintains backwards compatibility with legacy 802.11 standards and is able to deliver data rates up to 6.75Gbps in distances less than 10 meters. However when the distance between the Access Point (AP) and the receiver increases, 802.11ad employs the Fast Session Transfer Protocol that causes seamless fall back to the 5GHz and 2.4GHz bands so that end users experience uninterrupted connectivity at the same range as in today's WLANs but at decreased data rates. In this way, 802.11ad exploits the 60GHz spectrum only in very short, WPAN-similar ranges, thus falling short of providing 60GHz services into true WLAN formations.

B. Radio-&Fiber and Radio-over-Fiber schemes

Radio-&Fiber(R&F) architectures have emerged as the means to provide high-speed and omnipresent access networks that combine the flexibility and ubiquity of wireless connectivity with the long-distance and high data line-rate transmission properties of optical links[6][7]. R&F architectures consolidate existing optical and wireless infrastructures by attaching wireless APs to the Optical Network Units, whereas access to the two distinct media is controlled separately by employing two different MAC protocols with protocol translation taking place at their interface. Fiber/Wireless integration is a topic of major research interest and many approaches have been presented in the literature with the most predominant being EPON/GPON integration with WiMAX/LTE/DOCSIS[26]-[29] or 802.11[30] and mesh networks[31]-[32]. In that context, R&F approaches present the potential to provide high data transmission rates with minimal time delay since packets destined for intra-WLAN recipients remain in the WLAN territory whereas only inter-WLAN traffic traverses the fiber-based network. However R&F still requires the use of fully functioning intelligent APs at every ONU branch, therefore considerably increasing the costs for WLAN mm-wave

deployment. Note that traditional coverage extension solutions, such as the deployment of active repeaters, are not applicable in the millimeter wave paradigm since the high propagation losses of the 60 GHz signal would require the acquisition, configuration and maintenance of 30 times more hardware equipment compared to a 2.4-5 GHz network.

Alternatively, 60 GHz Radio-over-Fiber implementations stand as the most promising solution towards the deployment of unified, extended reach and multi-Gbps capable WLAN formations. Under the RoF paradigm the role of the AP is assumed by the Central Office (CO), which is attached through a fiber to a number of Remote Access Units (RAUs) that in turn provide 60 GHz broadband connectivity to mobile users (Fig.1). The RAU modules perform the optical-to-RF and RF-to-optical conversions, bringing in contact wireless clients and CO without employing any further intelligent operations, thus serving as "passive" gateways. In this way, RoF enables the formation of extended reach 60GHz WLANs, coming forward as the only solution that avoids the added cost of the active AP equipment deployment [20]-[23].

C. Wireless MACs over RoF

The direct application of current wireless protocols to the RoF realm poses a series of concerns regarding their compatibility with the dual medium architecture and raises issues concerning the optimal handling of both optical/wireless resources. Since RoF architectures place the AP at a distant location, optically propagated wireless signals are forced to travel significantly greater distances compared to the traditional Client-AP connection. Stretching the network size beyond the nominal wireless range can cause a detrimental effect on the MAC's operation due to the introduction of intolerable fiber delays [18],[19]. Furthermore, pure wireless access schemes are completely unaware of the underlying optical medium and therefore continuous RAU connectivity must be provided to assume proper operation. Considering that in picocellular mm-wave networks a fairly large number of RAUs must be employed to cover all premises in residential/corporate areas, lacking the necessary mechanisms to dynamically arbitrate the optical wavelengths leads to great resource squander and energy waste. The solution to the aforementioned problems lies with the introduction of a new generation of protocols that have been specifically tailored to operate and optimally arbitrate the dual-medium, such as the Medium Transparent MAC (MT-MAC) protocol that has been recently introduced [20],[22]. The MT-MAC protocol has been successfully demonstrated to operate under various wavelength availability conditions over both short bus topologies as well as long range tree infrastructures. To combat fiber delay impairments as well as to optimally arbitrate the 60 GHz spectrum, the MT-MAC protocol employs a Polling mechanism that has been shown to outperform classic CSMA/CA and TDMA schemes when operating in the mm-wave domain [33]. In addition the MT-MAC defines two distinct Contention Periods (CPs) to optimally regulate the concurrent access to both optical (wavelengths) and wireless media (wireless polls)

Fig.2:(a)The RAU design. (b)The data/control signal spectral arrangement. addressing the network from the RAU and end-user perspective respectively. A summary of the main MT-MAC protocol operational rules follows in Section IV-A.

III. PHYSICAL LAYER OVERVIEW

This section presents the 60 GHz RAU design, proposed for the MT-MAC-compatible RoF bus network. In the proposed scheme depicted in Fig.2(a), all RAUs employ a Coarse Wavelength Division Multiplexing (CWDM) demultiplexer in order to separate the optical signal into three spectral areas: i)1530-1550nm, ii)1550-1570nm and iii)1570-1590nm. The first band is reserved for the CW-MT-MAC control signals, while the second and third band channels carry the Downlink/Uplink (DL/UL) data signals from the CO, hereby referred as the Medium Transparent protocol Access Gate (MTAG), to the antenna units and vice versa. The DL data wavelengths are generated at the MTAG, while the UL data are generated by externally modulating a CW laser at the RAU, forming in this way l pairs, namely $\{\lambda_1, \lambda'_1\}, \{\lambda_2, \lambda'_2\}, \dots, \{\lambda_l, \lambda'_l\}$ that follow the spectral arrangement shown in Fig.2(b). In each wavelength pair, λ_l carries single-side-band (SSB) DL traffic at a 60GHz subcarrier from the MTAG to the RAU, while λ'_l carries UL traffic back to the MTAG. Similarly to the data wavelengths, the DL control signals are generated at the MTAG and the UL control signals at the RAU. The CW-MT-MAC control signals $\{\lambda_c, \lambda'_c\}$ are used for bandwidth allocation control operations: λ_c serves both for wireless

RAU Architecture	Control DL	Control UL	Data DL	Data UL
Based on Couplers[20][23]	12.5 dB	21 dB	9.7 dB	24.2dB
Based on Demux	5 dB	10 dB	3.2 dB	7.5dB

Fig.3: Total bus insertion losses for both RAU architectures versus the number of RAUs

signaling purposes as well as for wavelength tuning of the DL filter prior to the initiation of the next scheduled data session according to the CW-MT-MAC rules. At the same time, λ'_c carries signaling pulses from the wireless antenna units of each RAU to the MTAG thus notifying the latter regarding the pending uplink traffic requests from the wireless users. The wavelength pair allocation to each RAU is determined by the MTAG and broadcasted to the RAUs by use of the aforementioned control signals. Upon entering the RAU circuitry the control wavelengths λ_c and λ'_c are separated via an Arrayed Waveguide Grating (AWG). The DL control wavelength λ_c is fed into a photodiode where it is converted into an electrical signal. The electrical control signal is then wirelessly transmitted at 59.8GHz via a microwave antenna unit serving the CW-MT-MAC protocol contention operations in a way similar to the one described in [20]. The same signal drives a low-rate microcontroller (μ PC) which in turn tunes the downlink filter and the uplink laser to the allocated wavelengths. The DL data channels pass through an optical tunable filter [34] controlled by the μ PC which selects the wavelength λ_l . After Optical-to-Electrical conversion at the photodiode, the 60GHz signal is broadcasted by the microwave antenna to the wireless nodes located inside the RAU's range. The UL data wavelength λ'_l is generated through a tuneable laser controlled by the μ PC and is externally modulated with the user data that are received by the RAU's antenna before travelling back to the MTAG.

Table I summarizes the exhibited insertion losses for the signals described above and for two different RAU architectures. As it can be observed the newly proposed RAU architecture displays significantly lower insertion losses compared to the MT-MAC-supportive 60GHz "coupler-based" RAU design reported in [20]-[23]. Specifically, the insertion losses of the "coupler-based" RAU design are 24.2dB, defined by the UL data channel circuitry, while the insertion losses of the newly reported "based on Demux" RAU architecture are only 10dB, dictated by the respective losses of the UL control signal circuitry. Consequently, the RAU design reported here, offers an insertion loss reduction of up to 14.2dB compared to the previously reported design. RAU loss calculations have relied on insertion losses of respective commercially

available components, considering 2.5dB losses for every MUX/DEMUX element, 5dB losses per modulator, and 0.7dB losses for the tunable filter.

By adding up the power losses of each coupler in the bus with the fiber's propagation losses, we can calculate the total losses for each UL and DL channel. As reported in Table I, the UL Data channel in the coupler-based RAU and the UL control signal channel in the demux-based RAU are introducing the highest losses, representing the worst-case scenarios in terms of power budget requirements and therefore establishing the limiting factor for RAU population and network reach. Fig.3 depicts the total aggregated insertion losses for both RAU architectures versus the number of RAUs inserted in a bus topology network. The dotted black curve accounts the coupling losses in the bus access branch plus the fiber propagation losses (0.2dB/km) for all signals (Standard Losses). The blue curve declares the standard losses plus the insertion losses induced to the UL control signal by the demux-based RAU's circuitry, while the red dashed curve adds up the standard losses to the insertion losses introduced to the UL data signal in the coupler-based RAU architecture. The demux-based RAU architecture, displays significantly lower insertion loss, increasing this way the maximum number of RAUs that can be supported by the network for a given power budget. Specifically the proposed architecture inserts 10.3 dB RAU insertion losses (UL control) on top of the coupling and propagation losses, whereas the respective value for the coupler-based architecture in [20] is 46 dB (UL data). According to Fig.3, it can be concluded that for a power budget of 30 dB the proposed architecture can support up to 77 RAUs whereas the architecture in [20] can support up to 3 RAUs at most.

IV. THE CLIENT-WEIGHTED MT-MAC PROTOCOL

This section summarizes the main characteristics regarding the MT-MAC protocol's rules of operation that are in direct relation to the medium arbitration process. A more detailed and in depth description of the protocol is provided in [20]. In addition this section introduces the client-weighted allocation algorithm, which aims to balance the end user's perceived quality of experience.

A. MT-MAC Protocol Operational Rules

According to the protocol's specification all data exchange is regulated by the MTAG, which is connected through a fiber to a number of RAUs that in turn provide 60 GHz broadband connectivity to mobile users (Fig.1). To accommodate the medium's dual nature two distinct Contention Periods (CPs) are employed: the 1st CP aims in distributing the optical wavelengths amongst RAUs containing currently active wireless nodes, while the 2nd CP allocates the wireless capacity among them. At the beginning of the 1st CP, the MTAG emits a short beacon pulse in a specifically reserved channel, referred as the Control Channel, which in turn is broadcasted to all in-range wireless nodes using again a separate very narrow bandwidth channel utilized exclusively for control signaling. When nodes containing pending data detect the pulse, they respond immediately with a short pulse of the same

Fig. 4 a)The 1st Cont. Period b)SuperFrame, Resource Requesting Frame and Data Frame structure. Non shaded Resource Requesting Frames are optional.

duration. By collecting the received pulses and taking their receptions' time difference into account, as it is illustrated in Fig.4(a), the MTAG estimates which RAUs contain active nodes and allocates the wavelengths. The MTAG reschedules the 1st CP for execution every time new wavelengths become available and all known RAUs from the previous 1st CP run have been serviced.

Having acquired the full list of capacity demanding RAUs, the MTAG initiates the 2nd CP which is logically divided in SuperFrames (SFs), as it is depicted in Fig. 4(b). A SF contains two distinct and non-intermixing sets of frame types, namely the Resource Request Frames (RRFs) and the Data Frames (DFs), with the set of RRFs always preceding that of DFs. The DFs are responsible for carrying out the actual data transmission, whereas the RRFs' provide the MTAG with information regarding the number and IDs of each specific node prior to initiating any data exchange. The RRFs are further divided into m slots, with each slot comprising POLL, ID and ACK packets, following that particular order. At the beginning of each RRF all active nodes choose independently a random integer value y in the interval $[0, m)$, where y represents the number of POLL packets that must be received before responding with an ID packet. In the optimal case every node chooses a unique y value and transmits its respective ID packet in its own slot. Upon correct reception of the ID packet, the MTAG responds with an ACK, stating that this node has been successfully identified and therefore should not participate in any subsequent RRFs. However, a collision occurs when two or more nodes select the same value and as a result the MTAG refrains from transmitting an ACK, forcing these nodes' participation in the next RRF following immediately. The MTAG keeps transmitting RRFs until no collision occurs, effectively meaning that all active clients have been identified, ergo ending the 2nd CP. At this point the MTAG initiates the DATA_TX period where the main data exchange occurs in the form of a series of DFs transmissions until the end of the SF is reached. Note here that by taking advantage of the explicit polling nature, no

Fig. 5 CW-MT-MAC's flowchart.

inter-frame spaces are considered to exist between the transmitted packets and furthermore the DFs and RRFs are properly arranged by the MTAG to be of equal duration in the time domain. In addition, by exploiting the separate control channels, the 1st CP is run in parallel to the 2nd CP and therefore does not produce extra overhead.

B. The Client Weighted MT-MAC (CW-MT-MAC)

The protocol's enhanced user throughput and consequent delay fairness properties originate from the wavelength distribution algorithm implemented at the MTAG, taking advantage of the RoF's centralized network architecture that allows the latter to have full knowledge of the active clients residing in every RAU. Instead of the Round Robin Algorithm (RRA) employed so far in the MT-MAC approach of [20], the proposed CW-MT-MAC pursues a client-based approach to the wavelength-to-RAU distribution when the number of requesting RAUs R exceeds the number of available wavelengths w . The CW-MT-MAC mechanism is designed to distribute capacity based on the projected demand, which is considered analogous to the number of clients requesting traffic. As opposed to the static SF sizes employed by MT-MAT, CW-MT-MAC deploys SFs with variable durations, by assigning a transmission opportunity window (TX_OP) for every user demanding traffic at the specific point in time. For the purpose of choosing the next serviced RAU, CW-MT-MAC utilizes matrix A . A is always sorted in descending order regarding the number of the contained clients per RAU. In each row, a Utilization Counter (UC_q) indicates the total amount of serving time granted to RAU q . The higher the UC_q, the lowest the priority that RAU q has in the selection process. CW-MT-MAC's flowchart is depicted in Fig. 5. When a wavelength

becomes available, usually at the end of a SF, the MTAG checks by means of the 1st CP whether a RAU not present in A has requested a wavelength allocation (i.e. at least one end-user residing in RAU's range has pending data). If so, the MTAG resets all UC counters before inserting the RAU in A , but preserves their respective differences. For example if the UC values for RAUs 1, 2 and 3 are (9, 9, 7), with the addition of RAU 4 they become (2, 2, 0) and UC₄ initializes at 0. The latter aims in providing the newly inserted RAU with the maximum priority, enabling the MTAG to become rapidly acquainted with its properties (i.e. number of active/total nodes) and maintain A correctly updated. To commence the next SF, the MTAG chooses the RAU with the lowest UC value and, in case of a tie, the RAU with the highest number of active nodes, as the one to be served by the available wavelength. The length of the assigned SF in terms of frames is defined as $\alpha_q \cdot \text{TX_OP}$, where α_q is the number of active nodes that are participating in the current SF, and TX_OP is the length of the per user transmission opportunity window measured in polling frames. When the SF ends, UC_q is increased by α_q/τ_q , where τ_q is the total number of nodes residing in RAU q . The value τ_q is accumulatively calculated and updated as time progresses and different users become active within RAU q . In case α_q equals zero, meaning that the chosen RAU q had no active clients, UC_q is increased by 1, denoting that all users were served. If RAU q remains with no requesting clients for some time, then it is removed from A . It is essential to note here that, due to constraints applied by the Physical Layer, CW-MT-MAC is facing an upper barrier in certain extreme cases regarding the maximum achievable equalization of bandwidth. Even though densely populated RAUs can in theory be granted a larger portion of the available optical capacity, no more than one wavelength can be assigned to a single RAU, thus forming a maximum allocation limit. This limit effectively corresponds to the maximum number of users that can be served by a single RAU before overcoming CW-MT-MAC's operational capacity and is denoted as $n_{MAX}=z/w$, where z is the total number of active clients served by the MTAG. When the number of active nodes residing in a RAU surpasses n_{MAX} , CW-MT-MAC chooses to grant a dedicated wavelength to this RAU element for as long as the above condition applies. In this case, the CW-MT-MAC subtracts the dedicated wavelength and the number of users served by it and functions recursively for the remaining wavelengths and nodes.

Fig. 6 illustrates an execution example for 3 available wavelengths, 5 RAUs and a total of 16 users that are unevenly distributed amongst the RAUs as shown in matrix A . The figure depicts the wavelength-over-time allocation of

Fig. 6 CW-MT-MAC's operation example compared to MT-MAC. Utilization Counter (UC) refers only to the Client Weighted scenario. Different colors correspond to packets originating from different RAUs.

Fig. 7 Markov Model from the perspective of a single Remote Antenna Unit.

CW-MT-MAC versus the corresponding MT-MAC operation presented in [20]. As it can be noted, the MT-MAC equips each RAU with static 5-Data-Frame-long capacity “chunks” for the entire 25-Data-Frame-long running time, irrespective of the number of users served by each RAU. On the contrary, the CW-MT-MAC clearly differentiates and promotes the densely populated RAUs by reserving the wavelengths on a balanced user centric basis for the same period so as to provide fairness amongst the users, when the later occupy unevenly burdened RAUs.

C. CW-MT-MAC Markov Chain Model

This paragraph presents the mathematical analysis of the proposed scheme’s performance under saturated network traffic, assuming an ideal channel. The model described here is an enhanced version of the model presented in [21] that is capable to describe the CW-MT-MAC operation. Therefore only the features regarding the specifics of the optical capacity mechanisms are presented, whereas for the analysis regarding the wireless operation the reader should refer to [21].

We declare S to be the normalized system throughput, i.e. the ratio depicting the amount of time that the system transmits payload bits to the total amount of communication time. The above translates directly to the time portion that the system is located in the DATA_TX period of the SF. Therefore, S can be defined as

$$S = \frac{\Pi_{TX} T_{DF}}{\Pi_{CONT} T_{RRF} + \Pi_{TX} T_{DF}} \cdot (\Pi_{TX} + \Pi_{CONT}) \cdot \rho_{DF}, \quad \text{where}$$

Π_{TX} is the Steady State Probability (SSP) of the system being in the DATA_TX mode, Π_{CONT} is the SSP of the system being in the 2nd CP, T_{DF} and T_{RRF} are the durations of the DF and the RRF respectively, and ρ_{DF} is the payload information percentage contained in a DF. The latter is typically defined as $\rho_{DF} = L_{DATA} / (L_{POLL} + L_{DATA} + L_{ACK})$ where L_{DATA} , L_{POLL} and L_{ACK} are the size in bytes of the DATA, POLL and ACK packets respectively. In order to calculate Π_{TX} and Π_{CONT} we have deployed a 2D Markov chain model, depicted in Fig. 7, which demonstrates the scheme’s operation from the scope of a single RAU.

In the following analysis, we consider R RAUs sharing w available wavelengths. Each RAU contains n wireless users with z being the total number of users residing in the whole

system. The model’s nomenclature follows the $S_{i,k}$ symbolism, where i stands for the i th frame of the current SF and k is the number of nodes that are yet to be resolved through means of the 2nd CP. It should be noted that the *WAIT* state represents the optical waiting period, i.e. the state where the RAU does not have an assigned wavelength yet. The Markov chain model diagram can be logically divided into two areas. The first area is comprised of the state *WAIT*, whereas the second area is comprised of all the rest states. *WAIT*, being representative of the waiting period caused by the assignment/de-assignment of the optical wavelength, effectively controls the length of time that the current RAU lies in idle state. This signifies that its respective SSP is:

$$\Pi_{WAIT} = 1 - f \cdot w \quad (1)$$

where f is the function determining the allocation of the optical wavelengths. Under MT-MAC operation the w wavelengths are equally distributed among the R RAUs, whereas under CW-MT-MAC operation each RAU receives optical capacity directly proportional to the percentage of the total number of users it holds and therefore f becomes:

$$f = \begin{cases} 1/R & \text{(MT-MAC operation)} \\ n/z & \text{(CW-MT-MAC operation)} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

Regarding CW mode we derive that $n \leq z/w$ since $f \cdot w \leq 1$. The latter denotes the upper barrier or maximum number of users $n_{MAX} = z/w$ per RAU, above which CW-MT-MAC assigns a dedicated wavelength. Once being in the *WAIT* state the only possible actions are: to remain stationary with probability p_w while awaiting for wavelength assignment, or to enter the $S_{1,n}$ state with probability $\overline{p_w}$ once a wavelength has been assigned.

Following this, the wireless nodes enter the 2nd CP according to the rules described in Section III(A). All the wireless activity is depicted in the second logical area of the Markov model, which can be further divided into distinct rows and columns: each row corresponds to a single frame in the SF, while each column represents the number of nodes that are yet to be resolved in the 2nd CP. As such, the far-left column signifies the maximum number of unresolved nodes n and the far-right represents the situation where all nodes have been resolved, i.e. the number of unresolved nodes has reached zero. The expression describing the transition from state *WAIT* to state $S_{1,n}$ is:

$$\Pi_{1,n} = \Pi_{WAIT} \cdot \overline{p_w} \quad (3)$$

By (3) and the fact that each of the i frames, independently of its type, is of equal duration we derive that:

$$\Pi_{1,n} = \sum_k \Pi_{2,k} = \sum_k \Pi_{3,k} = \dots = \sum_k \Pi_{i,k} = f \cdot w / i \quad (4)$$

Using (1), (3) and (4), $\overline{p_w}$ is found to be:

$$\overline{p_w} = f \cdot w / (i \cdot (1 - f \cdot w)) \quad (5)$$

In the case of CW-MT-MAC employment (5) translates to $\overline{p_w} = n \cdot w / (i \cdot (z - n \cdot w))$ whereas in the case of RRA it becomes $\overline{p_w} = w / (i \cdot (R - w))$. Finally in order to calculate S

Fig. 8 Node population distributions for five different standard deviations.

we need to specify Π_{TX} , Π_{CONT} , T_{RRF} and T_{DF} values, that are directly depended on (1) and (3) as well as on the specifics of the wireless access control scheme and therefore their estimation is considered outside the scope of this paper. Please refer to [21] for details regarding their analytic calculation.

V. NETWORK PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

This section presents the performance of the client-weighted algorithm when applied on the MT-MAC protocol for a RoF-over-bus topology. The test configuration comprises 10 RAUs with the distance between the first RAU and the MTAG equal to 500m and 50m fiber intervals amongst the RAU modules, producing a total network length of 950m. This architecture is compatible with network deployments in indoor domestic or small enterprise environments, where a common MTAG is considered to serve multiple rooms over a single fiber bus providing a discrete RAU connectivity point to every room. An event-driven simulator was implemented in Java with the full simulation parameters employed being summarized in Table II. The total number of users located in the system equals to 50, distributed using an approximation of the normal distribution properly adjusted to produce discrete values that provides “bell-shaped” populations with mean value $\mu=5$ users per RAU. We tested five different user distribution patterns, starting from the least dispersed (uniform) distribution with standard deviation $\sigma=0$ and gradually migrating to the most dispersed distribution with standard deviation $\sigma=4.5$, as depicted in Fig. 8. In order to stress test the algorithm’s functionalities for the whole network length, the users’ distributions always abide by the rule of having at least one user per RAU. Furthermore, the channel is considered to operate under ideal conditions and all users are equipped with buffers in order to accommodate generated traffic. Each RAU module is considered to have

TABLE II: SIMULATION PARAMETERS			
Fiber Prop. Delay	1 μ s per 200m	Air Prop. Delay	0.16 μ s
Slots in RRF	10	ACK Size	8 bytes
DATA Size	1288 bytes	ID, POLL Size	64 bytes
Data Bitrate	1 Gbps	Buffer Size	80 pack.
Mean Burst Length	1.5 Kbytes	Burst Length Std. Deviation	1,42 Kbytes
CWA TX_OP Size	30 packets	RRA SF Size	150 packets

3m effective radius. Since the presented framework implies a dynamic capacity allocation scheme, a shortage of wavelengths towards the number of existing RAUs in the network is always taken into consideration and denoted henceforth as the wavelength availability factor w/R . This shortage is imposed by the mm-wave nature of the wireless medium which generally presumes a large amount of very short ranged RAUs serviced by a lesser number of wavelengths either due to scale or due to energy efficiency reasons. In order to better simulate IP traffic, the employed packet generator is based on a bursty traffic model exhibiting long-tail properties, meaning generated traffic is characterized by high deviation from the distribution’s mean value of burst length. As presented in detail in Table II, for the current experimental set we considered a mean burst length of 1.5kB, with the employed traffic generation algorithm producing a standard deviation of 1,42kB. Due to this high deviation, the per user TX_OP window was chosen to be 30 frames long (~4kB), so as to be certain that the majority of the generated bursts would fit into a single SF. In accordance, the RRA SF size was set to 150 frames long, a value that was inferred by multiplying the corresponding CW-MT-MAC transmission opportunity window with the users’ distribution mean $\mu=5$.

A. Performance under saturation conditions

Fig.9(a) depicts the saturation throughput results obtained by both the analytical model and the respective simulation tool for the CW-MT-MAC scheme, for various optical capacity availability factors denoted by the ratio w/R , ranging from 0.1 to 0.9 and for the two most extreme distributions with $\sigma=0$ and $\sigma=4.47$, respectively. As can be noted the curves and symbols practically overlap each other, denoting that in saturation conditions CW-MT-MAC exhibits equal performance at the system level, irrespective of the client distribution pattern. In addition, Fig.9(a) displays the excellent matching existing between the

Fig. 9 a) User throughput vs. w/R ratio b) Throughput per user for all participating users of the network c) User throughput and its standard deviation vs. the user distribution standard deviation.

analytical results and the respective simulation-based findings, experiencing only negligible differences up to a maximum of 3%. This good agreement between theory and simulation confirms the validity of the model, revealing also the linear dependence existing between throughput and the optical availability ratio w/R . CW-MT-MAC yields an efficiency rate of almost 92% (throughput to load), a fact that is indicative of the nearly optimum capacity exploitation in this dual-medium platform.

Fig.9(b) presents the average throughput for each of the 50 participating users in the network, when the later are spread out using the distribution with $\sigma=2.05$. As can be clearly observed, CW-MT-MAC manages to level out all throughput deliverance irrespective of the inequalities inserted into the network from the uneven client populations. In comparison, classic MT-MAC exhibits great disproportion regarding capacity allocation where the majority of clients residing in crowded RAUs receive less-than-average throughput opportunities, whereas the small fraction of clients that are in less-occupied areas receive up to four times greatest share. The above behavior undermines the network's efficiency as a whole, since users residing in different RAUs perceive a highly varying resource availability depending on their current location.

This variation can be more fully visualized in Fig.9(c) where the mean throughput per user as well as its standard deviation for all distribution patterns of Fig. 8 and for $w/R=0.5$ is depicted. As it can be noted, the mean throughput remains constant regardless of the clients' distribution, but the case is totally different when coming to the standard deviation of the later, where CW-MT-MAC exhibits significantly lower throughput deviations compared to MT-MAC. MT-MAC's σ -values equal zero only in the case of the uniform user distribution pattern, and increase rapidly as the users get unevenly distributed amongst the system's RAUs, showing the latter's inefficiency towards accommodating irregular populations in RoF networks. On the other hand CW-MT-MAC's σ -values remain zero for the first four user distribution patterns where the number of clients n is always lower than $n_{MAX}=10$. When overcoming this point, CW-MT-MAC dedicates a wavelength to all RAUs having $n>n_{MAX}$ clients, which produces inequalities

and therefore deviation of throughput. However the latter always delivers the best possible throughput uniformity, offering a clear advantage and fairer throughput delivery.

B. Performance under non saturation conditions

Fig. 10 depicts the protocol's non-saturation performance versus various optical availability factors designated by the w/R ratio (Fig.10(a) and 10(b)), ranging from 0.1 and up to 0.9 as well as versus various traffic loads(Fig.10(c) and 10(d)), ranging from 10% up to 100% of the maximum theoretical network capacity. Both CW-MT-MAC and MT-MAC were tested for the most extreme user distribution depicted in Fig.8 with standard deviation $\sigma=4.5$. As demonstrated by the respective legends all results in Fig.10(a) and 10(b) can be logically classified into groups depending on the offered load. Accordingly results in Fig.10(c) and 10(d) are clustered based on the respective w/R ratio. As can be noted in the 30% load case depicted in Fig. 10(a), throughput follows a linear path until it reaches its maximum value when the w/R ratio exceeds the offered load, effectively meaning that all traffic is accommodated due to the optical wavelength abundance. The same applies in the curves group depicting the 80% load scenario, with the difference being that linear properties continue for higher loads until again the point where the w/R ratio exceeds the offered load. Regarding the MT-MAC/CW-MT-MAC comparison we notice a borderline superiority of the second over first one. Specifically, CW-MT-MAC exhibits a marginal throughput gain in the 30% load scenario, whereas the gain increases and reaches its highest value of 5% in the 80% load scenario. This performance boost is the result of the proportional wavelength assignment mechanism which administers optical capacity not statically but in accordance to the received bandwidth claims. In this way, possible idle times in less crowded RAUs are avoided while the much needed service time is extended in the densely populated areas. This performance agreement is also evident in Fig. 10(b) which depicts the mean packet delay. As can be noted, delay outcomes start at very high values while the offered load exceeds the available optical capacity ratio due to the traffic being many times greater than the maximum theoretical capacity achievable by the available wavelengths. However as the wavelength availability rises, delay follows a decreasing slope, with the curves corresponding to 30% load dropping at higher rates than the high-load 80% scenario. By comparing CW-MT-MAC's and MT-MAC's outcomes it becomes clear that, when population distribution is uneven amongst RoF's antennas, the first manages to attain higher metrics, especially while the w/R ratio remains lower than the offered load, confirming that service balancing amongst uneven population distributions can indeed lead to better overall system level performance.

Fig.10(c) and 10(d) illustrate the protocol's behavior versus various traffic loads, ranging from 10% up to 100% for the most extreme user distribution deviation. CW-MT-MAC's and MT-MAC's performance was tested for two different wavelength availability factors w/R , namely 0.3 and 0.8. Fig. 10(c) presents the total system throughput versus various load conditions, revealing the linear exploit

Fig. 11 a) MT-MAC protocol User Throughput and Mean User Delay Performance with their respective Standard Deviations vs. the User's Distribution Standard Dev. b) CW-MT-MAC protocol User Throughput and Mean User Delay Performance with their respective Standard Deviations vs. the User's Distribution Standard Dev.

of the dual-medium while the offered load remains well under the corresponding w/R ratio. As load increases though, throughput forms around its saturation plateau, since all traffic beyond that point is limited by the respective w/R ratio. Delay outcomes presented in Fig. 10(d) remain minimal while load is below w/R and increase rapidly when load approaches the later. After the offered load has exceeded w/R , delay follows an increasing course before saturating at its maximum value, since all exceeding traffic beyond this point transforms directly to dropped packets, that are not taken into consideration in the delay calculation. Regarding the comparison between the two competing schemes we notice again a marginal but constant performance differentiation in favor of CW-MT-MAC. This performance thrust highlights that when faced with uneven populations, traffic provision and service distinction are in order to achieve optimum operation.

Fig. 11 offers a more detailed observation of the protocol's performance as the latter is perceived from the user's perspective. In addition, it provides insight on how this performance fluctuates when gradually transitioning from uniform to uneven distribution of the network's nodes. The displayed results show the protocol's performance for both CW-MT-MAC and classic MT-MAC at the user level versus the user distribution's standard deviation σ . The σ -values utilized correspond to the distribution patterns displayed in Fig. 9 and the results are shown for $w/R=0.5$ and 50% traffic load conditions. Fig. 11(a) illustrates the mean user throughput and its respective standard deviation for both protocols. As it can be noted, not only does CW-MT-MAC achieve higher and more consistent throughput output, but its main advantage lies in the latter's standard deviation, where it exhibits significantly lower deviations compared to the MT-MAC. In agreement to the respective saturation outcomes, MT-MAC's σ -value approaches zero only for the uniform user distribution pattern, whereas CW-MT-MAC's σ -value succeeds in remaining zero for the first four user distribution patterns where the number of clients n is always lower than n_{MAX} . When overcoming this point, CW-MT-MAC dedicates a wavelength to all RAUs having

Fig. 12 a) User throughput vs. User Id b) User mean packet delay and its standard deviation for each of the 50 users of the network

$n > n_{MAX}$ clients, which produces inequalities and therefore deviation of throughput. However, CW-MT-MAC clearly retains the edge over MT-MAC by offering the minimum possible deviation and therefore fairer throughput delivery. The above are also reflected in the respective mean user packet delay results displayed in Fig. 11(b), where CW-MT-MAC clearly maintains the advantage of significantly lower delay and their respective σ -values, ergo confirming the proposed scheme's increased fairness capabilities.

A more comprehensive look on CW-MT-MAC's fairness properties internals can be derived by means of Fig. 12, which presents the above mentioned metrics for each of the 50 participating users in the bus topology network for the case of $\sigma=2.05$, $w/R=0.5$ and 50% traffic load. Fig. 12(a) presents the achieved user's throughput where it is clearly evident that MT-MAC exhibits great disproportion regarding capacity allocation and remains heavily depended on the user's distribution. On the contrary CW-MT-MAC manages to level out all service deliverance irrespective of the inequalities inserted into the network from the uneven client distribution. Fig. 12(b) displays the per user mean packet delay and their respective intra-packet delay variation metrics. As it can be noted not only does CW-MT-MAC offer an almost constant delay amongst the participating nodes of the network regardless of the grade of population's dissimilarity but also CW-MT-MAC's observed delay is subject to smaller, strictly uniform and consistent delay variations. This fact highlights that CW-MT-MAC is a better fit towards supporting modern real-time applications, e.g., VoIP, since PDV can be a serious issue affecting delay-restricted applications.

VI. CONCLUSION

We have presented a new user fairness-enabling MT-MAC protocol and a novel RAU design for the realization of efficient and fair Gbps-range 60 GHz RoF WLAN networks. Fairness is achieved by equipping the protocol with the user-centric Client Weighted Algorithm for the optical capacity arbitration procedures. Rapid improvement on user throughput and delay equalization is demonstrated for various network conditions through analytical and simulation performance analysis for different user distribution patterns and loads under specific wavelength availability constraints.

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